

MODIFIED BY WOOD FILLERS RECYCLED POLYETHYLENE FOR EUROPALLETS APPLICATION

Stanislaw Kuciel, Magdalena Proszek, Wieslaw Dziadur

Krakow University of Technology, POLAND

Division of Experimental Mechanics and Biomechanics, Warszawska 24, 31-155 Krakow

SUMMARY: One of the possibilities of reinforcement of polyolefines is adding diverse fillers like glass or carbon fibers (but they are rather expensive) and natural fillers like wood, plants and others. It's especially important for wasted of low density polyethylene which has low modulus. For the tests it was used waste polyethylene (LDPE) from industrial and consumption films and as reinforcement it was used wood fibers LIGNOCEL CB 120 supplied by J. Rettenmaier & Söhne GmbH+Co. This filler is made of coniferous soft trees, it has fibrous structure and its particle size is 70 – 150 μm . For the tests it was prepared three kinds of composite materials with 10% (PE1), 20% (PE2) and 30% (PE3) of wood fibers. Besides for comparison it was tested original polyethylene (PE0) and next was tested specimens cut out from produced europallets (with 15% of wood fibers). It was tested mechanical properties all prepared composite materials like tensile strength, stress and bending e-modulus, impact strength, Brinell hardness and processing properties like melt flow, Vicat point and additionally density (balance of liquid method), water absorption and photos on optical and SEM microscope. Tests of mechanical properties during tension and bending show that properties connected with increasing of straight and stiffness like e-modulus, tensile strength, hardness grow along with content of wood fibers. However properties like strain at break or impact strength low with increase of amount of fillers. The Vicat point of tested composite materials was on the level about 98 – 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and it doesn't change with increase of amount of fillers. Results of melt flow presents fall of processing properties along with increase content of wood fibers. Using image analyzes it was shown distribution of wooden fibers for all tested composite materials. After comparison of all tests' results we proposed one composite with 15% of wood fibers and reclaimed LDPE that to process pre-production batch of europallet produced by Becker GmbH (extraction with pressing). Besides its distribution of stresses and deflections of europallets was analyzed having various amount of wood fibers (by means of FEM - finite elements method) that to estimate their strength (HMH hypothesis) and reduction cost of material processing. Geometric and numeric models of analyzed pallets and bitches prepared by means of Femap 7.1, calculations and postprocessing by Ansys 5.7. The low-filler reclaimed polyethylene can be used on such products like wood decks, boxes, flower pots, automotive parts and others building and building parts. On the base of done tests and numerical calculation it seems that filling of reclaimed LDPE by wood fibers has to be on the level 15 – 20% for optimal processing and properties.

KEYWORDS: Environmental concerns, Mechanical & physical properties, Reinforcements

INTRODUCTION

Possibilities of reusing and developing of waste plastics are one of the main problems of waste management for municipal government especially in the context of adapting Polish law to standards of EC [16]. During the last 10 years total amount of plastics waste increased twice, especially in communal agglomerations. Among communal waste plastics make up 7 to 14% of whole their mass and 30% of their volume [8,16]. Amount of all communal waste for instance in the region of Krakow exceed level of 250 thousands of tons per year and during last ten years increased three times. Plastics make up over 13% of their mass (according to research of MPO – Municipal Waste Plant) what gives about 32.5 thousands tons of waste per year and it's near 32 kilos per person [8]. That level of waste plastics is similar to amount which is reached in high industrial countries of EC. It dominates waste of packing mainly polyolefines (PP, HDPE and LDPE – with total amount about 23%: it gives about 8000 tons per year), polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polystyrene (PS). We can observed little fall

of amount of unseparate PVC waste what is very good of course [8,16]. Looking at the dynamism of economy development, the increasing amount of separate waste, ecological education, improved the waste legislation we can predict continuous plastics' increase in communal waste until 2010. Plastic wastes appear in different places, usually in places their processing, market and industrial centers, construction industry and mainly in millions of households. They are diverse with regard to quality, clarity and usefulness to reprocessing. Reclaimed plastics can't be used as products which have contact with food or as high demands esthetic and hygienic products, they also shouldn't be applied as short-time used products because they quickly come back to plastics store-place. Reclaimed plastics have lower properties than virgin plastics – mainly the strength falls with the simultaneous fall of modules and increase fragile especially for PP, PE, PS and PET [16]. One of the possibilities of reinforcement of polyolefines is adding diverse fillers [1,16,2,3,12,13,14] like glass or carbon fibers (but they are rather expensive) and natural fillers like wood, plants and others [10]. It's especially important for wasted of low density polyethylene which has low modulus [8,13].

MATERIAL, PROCESSING AND KINDS OF COMPOSITES

For the tests it was used waste polyethylene (LLDPE + LDPE) from industrial and consumption films and as reinforcement it was used wood fibers LIGNOCEL CB 120 supplied by J. Rettenmaier & Söhne GmbH+Co [4]. This filler is made of coniferous soft trees, it has fibrous structure and its particle size is 70 – 150 µm. Others characteristic quantities it's: residue after roasting (0,5%), coefficient pH (5,5), bulk density (100 – 145 g/l) and residual humidity (≤ 6%) [4], [5]. For the tests it was prepared three kind of compositions with 10% (PE1), 20% (PE2) and 30% (PE3) of wood fibers [4,5]. Besides for comparison it was tested original polyethylene (PE0) and next was tested specimens cut out from produced europallets (with 15% of wood fibers) [8]. That to prepare granulated compositions for injection we mixed wood fibers and polyethylene using standard lines for granulation in Plant of Plastics Processing in Klaj. Specimens for the tests were injected by ZA Tarnow S.A. Next using that specimens we tested mechanical properties all prepared compositions like tensile strength, stress and bending e-modulus, impact strength, Brinell hardness and processing properties like melt flow, Vicat point and additionally density (balance of liquid method) and photos on optical and SEM microscope.

RESULTS OF TESTS

Tests of mechanical properties [11] during tension and bending show that properties connected with increasing of straight and stiffness like e-modulus, tensile strength, hardness grow along with content of wood fibers. It's shown in Fig.1.

However properties like strain at break or impact strength low with increase of amount of fillers. The dependencies of this properties are shown in Fig.2.

Fig.1 Comparison of tensile (E) and bending (E_g) modulus and tensile strength (σ_m) for various kinds of compositions and reclaimed polyethylene.

The Vicat point of tested composites was on the level about 98 – 100 °C and it doesn't change with increase of amount of fillers. Results of melt flow presents fig.3. SEM micrographs of surface (fractures and polished cross-sections) of example kinds of composites are shown in Fig.4, 5.

Fig.2 Comparison of strain at break and impact strength for various kinds of composites.

Fig.3 Results of measurement of melt flow (MFR/190°C/2.16) tested composites.

Fig.4 SEM micrographs of (a)-single wood fibre (fracture, x500) and (b)-distribution of fibres in the polyethylene matrix for PE2 composite (polished cross-section, x300)

Fig.5 SEM micrographs of (a)-surface of composite with 20% wood fibres (fracture, x1000) and (b)-interface region between wood fibres and LDPE after soaking in the water (polished cross-section, x1000)

Fig.6 Comparison of density for tested various kinds of composites and reclaimed polyethylene.

Fig.7 Increase of water absorption for various kinds of material.

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS OF PALLETS DEFLECTION

After comparison of all tests' results we proposed one composite with 15% of wood fibers and reclaimed LDPE that to process pre-production batch of europallet produced by Becker GmbH (extraction with pressing). Besides it distribution of stresses and deflections of europallets was analyzed having various amount of wood fibers (by means of FEM - finite elements method [6,9]) that to estimate their strength (HMH hypothesis) and reduction cost of material processing. It was assumed that application of continuous loading was 10000N on the surface of pallets [7]. It was analyzed two kinds of supports: first on the external skids of pallets and second on classical support of fork-lift truck. Geometric and numeric models of analyzed pallets and batch files prepared by means of Femap 7.1, calculations and postprocessing by Ansys 5.7. – simples of calculations presents Fig.8, 9 [8,17].

PE3

Fig.8 Deflection of pallet for the second kind of support.

PE3

Fig.9 Distribution of pallet's stresses for the second kind of support.

Fig.10 it is shown how max. deflection changes in depend of amount wood fibers and pallet's kind of support. Besides it was analyzed distributions of stresses for both proposed kinds of support and all tested materials. It turned out that the stresses change little during lifting weighted pallet by the truck but much changes appear for pallets with support on the external skids. Additionally before choice of composites it was tested the water absorption and results of its was shown in Fig.7.

Fig.10 Comparison of max. deflections of various kinds of supports.

After mechanical and numerical analyzes it was proposed to make pallets of such composites: reclaimed LDPE with 15% of wood fibers and reclaimed LDPE with 20% of reclaimed HDPE. Comparison of deflections for two kinds of supports of pallets made of proposed composites was shown in Fig.11.

B)

Fig.11 Comparison of deflections for two kinds of supports of pallets made of proposed composites.

CONCLUSION

In this article it estimated possibilities reinforced reclaimed LDPE by natural wood fibres and possibilities its processing in using on large products (like europallets) on standard processing lines. Mechanical properties especially stiffness increase along with amount of fillers. It makes that impact strength and strain falls little until 20% wood fibres. Along with increase of fillers it grows the water absorption. On the base of done tests and numerical calculation it seems that filling of reclaimed LDPE by wood fibres has to be on the level 15 – 20% for optimal processing and properties. The low-filler reclaimed polyethylenes can be use on such products like wood decks, boxes, flower pots, automotive parts and others building and roading parts [3]. It seems interesting to continue testing proposed composites which demand next tests like: creep tests and estimation of mechanical, physical and using properties after soaking in the water. Using the thermoplastic polymer waste for PWM production solves three problem at once: 1) preventing environment pollution by means of polymer waste recycling, 2) obtaining new materials suitable for goods production, 3) possibilities its utilization by the way of combustion [15].

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